

Microtasks: UX design improvements

Background & definitions

Before starting our work with ACTION, we had already run a small number of experimental quests/microtasks, such as [MobiFix](#). Each microtask focused on analysing data about certain categories of device in our community-powered database of repair attempts. It was largely due to the success of these early experiments that we applied to the ACTION accelerator.

However, much of the feedback we received about these microtasks focused around the user experience (UX) of the task; many participants found them difficult to understand and use and often offered helpful feedback for improvements.

Funding from ACTION not only allowed us to produce more of these microtasks, but also dedicate more time to improving the UX. We felt this would be an important part of our work to help both us and our participants to get the most out of each microtask by reducing frustration and increasing engagement with the data.

From the first microtask, we set up custom analytics to help inform our UX design work. Our aim for this work was to monitor how engaged participants were with the task. The most pertinent metrics for this report are:

Average opinions per logged in user

The number of opinions submitted by participants who were signed into our community platform divided by the number of participants who were signed into our community platform. To measure this, we used a custom analytics dashboard on our Metabase platform.

Average opinions per anonymous user session

The number of opinions during anonymous user sessions (participants not signed into our community platform) divided by the number of anonymous user sessions. To measure this, we used a custom analytics dashboard on our Metabase platform. Note that because anonymous users were not tracked, we can only measure opinions per session; it is possible for one anonymous user to complete more than one session.

Bounce Rate

The percentage of single-page sessions in which there was no interaction with the page. A bounced session has a duration of 0 seconds. To measure this, we used Google Analytics.

% Exit

The number of exits divided by the number of pageviews for the page. It indicates how often users exit the site from that page when they view the page. To measure this, we used Google Analytics.

Microtask #1: PrintCat

Our first ACTION microtask focused on categorising problems with printers seen at community repair events. Printers are one of the most emotive devices; many people have had frustrating experiences dealing with printers that don't work as expected. We wanted to reach as many participants as possible, we focused on adding more instructional text, making the UX as bug-free as possible and adding support for more languages than previous microtasks.

Improvements made:

- We added new instructional text above the task to help participants understand what to do. Also included a link to the 'about' page, which contained further information and instructions.
- We internationalised the microtask, adding support for five additional languages for the first time (the previous task only supported English). We translated the interface into: French, Dutch & German, Italian and Spanish to reach a broader audience and make it more accessible to our partners in the Netherlands and Germany.
- We fixed bugs & errors from previous microtask (especially around translation and displaying special characters).
- We improved the sharing preview (the text and image that appears when the link is embedded on external sites like Facebook & Twitter) and included a custom logo for the first time (as above).
- We added proper buttons for accessing the status and about pages (replacing the previous cute, but ultimately confusing cat icon and 'i' symbol).
- We added a pop-up modal for participants who completed 5 records and were not signed in to the platform encouraging them to register to save their progress and learn more about repair by joining the community
- We made sure the task closed properly - when a participant has seen all records or when the task is complete, they would be shown a 'We're all done here, thanks' message
- We wrote clearer instructions in our wider communication about the microtask, e.g. in [the forum post announcement](#).
- We set up analytics dashboards for PrintCat and future microtasks to help us monitor engagement and make more informed decisions about future UX development.

- We added information about the source of the data in the form of Open Repair Alliance branding at the bottom of the page.

Before:

After:

About PrintCat

PrintCat is a web app to **collaboratively categorise the type of faults in printers brought to community events** such as Restart Parties and Repair Cafés.

The [Open Repair Alliance](#) was set up by anstiftung, Fixit Clinic, Repair Café Foundation, Repair Cafe Wales and The Restart Project to create a joint open standard to collect and share data from community repair activities.

Volunteers collect data about the devices that are brought into our repair events. The data is uploaded to platforms like Restarters.net, Repair Monitor and Reparatur Initiativen and [aggregated as Open Data](#) by the Open Repair Alliance.

To enable community repair to contribute to the current push for right to repair regulations for tablets, we want to see what types of faults are commonly encountered.

So we'd like to analyse the data collected so far, to learn about key faults seen at repair events - and this is where you can help, by playing PrintCat!

Find out more, and give us your feedback, in the [PrintCat discussion](#).

Impact on engagement:

PrintCat worked well with members of our community (participants who were logged into our platform), with each participating community member submitting an average of 48 opinions.

However, anonymous participants seemed to struggle, submitting an average of just 5 opinions per user. See the [final section](#) below for more detail. We decided that this would need to be a priority for the next microtask, TabiCat.

We also noted that the bounce rate (of 5.56%) and % exit rate (of 8.74%) were a little higher than we'd have liked, implying that a significant proportion of users were leaving the page without interacting with it (bounce rate) or not exploring the rest of the community platform afterwards (% exit rate - leaving the site after that page).

	Average opinions per logged in user	Average opinions per anonymous user session	Bounce Rate	% Exit
PrintCat	48	5	5.56%	8.74%

Microtask #2: TabiCat

Our second ACTION microtask, TabiCat, built on the first. This time, we wanted to look at tablets (like iPads) and e-readers.

One of the main pieces of feedback was that participants got frustrated by the poor quality of some of the source data, and would simply leave the task. So, for TabiCat we decided to address this and make further refinements focused on participants who were newer to this work (especially given the low opinions/user rate for anonymous users from PrintCat). Planning for this microtask began as soon as PrintCat launched meaning we couldn't address every piece of feedback, but we did make the following improvements...

Improvements made:

- To address feedback about the low quality of some of the source data, we added a 'poor data' button, allowing participants to report records that didn't contain enough information. We made this button obvious by changing its colour to red and moving it to a separate line from the rest of the options:

- We added a series of 'Did you know...?' messages to offer participants more information about repair and our objectives in bite-sized snippets.

- We added a percentage completion indicator to the status page of the microtask to help participants understand and follow our progress:

- We removed the 'Translate button' for records that appeared in the participant's own language (to remove visual clutter).
- We added a survey that popped up after a handful of records to learn more about participants and provide this data to the ACTION team.
- We moved the confirmation button above the list of options to make it easier to see for people using mobile devices.
- We fixed a small bug that made navigation harder on mobile.
- We improved the visual guide to using the microtask in our announcement topic on our forum in response to a suggestion from the first ACTION diversity & inclusion call.

Impact on engagement:

The metrics for TabiCat implied that our focus on anonymous users did work to increase participation; while anonymous users contributed an average of 5 opinions per session for PrintCat, they contributed an average of 19 opinions per session for TabiCat.

However, the average number of opinions submitted by logged-in community members actually fell from 48 in PrintCat to 40 in TabiCat. Given logged-in users provide many more opinions per person, we wanted to address this decrease with BattCat and decided to re-prioritise community members.

We were also pleased to see the bounce rate and % Exit rate both fall by around 3%, implying that a smaller proportion of users were leaving the page without interacting with it and were increasingly visiting other sections of the website before leaving it.

	Average opinions per logged in user	Average opinions per anonymous user session	Bounce Rate	% Exit
PrintCat	48	5	5.56%	8.74%
TabiCat	40	19	2.00%	5.89%

Microtask #3: BattCat

Our third and final ACTION microtask was a little different. Instead of investigating why devices had broken, we wanted to learn about barriers to repair for battery-powered devices in general. This meant we had to ask different questions depending on whether each record contained information about an end of life device or a repairable device.

- For end of life devices, we wanted to know “What prevented this device from being repaired?”
- For repairable devices, we wanted to know “What are the next steps?”

In order to make the microtask as accessible as possible, we decided to create a new visual design that would address feedback from PrintCat and TabiCat, remain consistent with the design language of the rest of the site and allow us to alternate between these two questions without confusing participants. We were also mindful to retain all the minor visual and functional improvements developed over the previous microtasks.

The metrics for TabiCat implied that our focus on anonymous users did work to increase participation; while anonymous users contributed an average of 5 opinions each for PrintCat, they contributed an average of 19 opinions each for TabiCat. However, the average number of opinions submitted by logged-in community members actually fell from 48 to 40. We wanted to address this decrease with BattCat and decided to re-prioritise community members.

Improvements made:

- We removed the line of help text at the top, which many participants didn’t actually read. Instead we:
 - Changed the page title to give some indication of what the task was for
 - Included significantly more help text next to each action required on the page with big numbers to indicate the two steps required for each record.
- We improved our data-cleaning process, removing additional types of poor data from the task in advance in order to reduce the quantity of poor data encountered by participants.
- We used colour-coding in addition to text to visually distinguish the two type of device (and question) that could be displayed

- We added labels to the bits of information displayed about each device (e.g. 'Device' and 'Brand') to help participants understand more clearly what they were.
- We added a 'percentage complete' indicator to the main microtask page to help participants feel a sense of progress while working through the task.
- We removed the 'Did you know..?' messages, as participants reported finding them too overwhelming in TabiCat.

Before agreeing on a final design, we worked through a number of iterations:

Versions 1, 3 and 5:

1. **BattCat** STATUS ABOUT

We've collected data on lots of broken battery-powered devices from community repair events. We need your help to learn how they broke so we know how to make them easier to fix in the future. [Learn more](#).

1 Read the information about the broken device.
Someone brought this broken device to a community repair event.

Device: tablet Description of problem: "The battery died. Needs replacing, but no way to open the device."
Brand: Amazon
Status: End of life Translate

2 What prevented this device from being repaired?
Select the option that best fits the problem described above...

battery unavailable corroded beyond repair damaged while replacing battery
difficult to open price of spare battery unreplaceable battery
unreplaceable battery charger other
not enough information I don't know

3. **BattCat** STATUS ABOUT

We've collected data on lots of broken battery-powered devices from community repair events. We need your help to learn how they broke so we know how to make them easier to fix in the future. [Learn more](#).

1 Read the information about the broken device.
Someone brought this broken device to a community repair event.

Device: tablet Description of problem: "The battery died. Needs replacing, but no way to open the device."
Brand: Amazon
Status: End of life Translate

2 What prevented this device from being repaired?
Select the option that best fits the problem described above...

battery unavailable corroded beyond repair damaged while replacing battery
difficult to open price of spare battery unreplaceable battery
unreplaceable battery charger other
not enough information I don't know

5. **BattCat** STATUS ABOUT

We've collected data on lots of broken battery-powered devices from community repair events. We need your help to learn how they broke so we know how to make them easier to fix in the future. [Learn more](#).

1 Read the information about the broken device.
Someone brought this broken device to a community repair event.

Device: tablet Brand: Amazon Status: Repairable
Description of problem: "The battery died. Needs replacing, but we didn't have a spare one to hand."
Translate

2 What prevented this device from being repaired?
Select the option that best fits the problem described above...

clean battery contacts fix connectors or casing fix the charging port
replace the battery replace the charger or charging cable
battery is not the main problem other
not enough information I don't know

Here's what the new design looked like in the end (version 6):

Repairable device

BattCat: categorise battery problems

STATUS ABOUT

1

Read the information about the broken device.
A volunteer tried to fix this device at a community repair event and wrote this description.

Device: Vacuum Status: **Repairable**

Description of problem:
No enciende - Hay que cambiar y soltar baterias nuevas

Translate

2

What are the next steps?
Select the option that best fits the problem described above.

Battery is not the main problem Clean battery contacts Fix connectors or casing

Fix the charging port Replace the charger or charging cable

Replace with new battery Other Poor data

I don't know →

Our progress
The percentage of devices we have classified so far

81.8%

Powered by data from:
OPEN REPAIR ALLIANCE

End of life device

BattCat: categorise battery problems

STATUS ABOUT

1

Read the information about the broken device.
A volunteer tried to fix this device at a community repair event and wrote this description.

Device: Vacuum Brand: Black & Decker Status: **End of life**

Description of problem:
Batterijen zijn op; hoe krijg ik dit open

Translate

2

What prevented this device from being repaired?
Select the option that best fits the problem described above.

Battery is not the main problem Battery not readily available

Built-in or soldered battery, cannot remove Charger not readily available

Damaged while replacing battery Difficult to remove battery

New battery too expensive Unrepairable corrosion or leakage Other

Poor data

I don't know →

Our progress
The percentage of devices we have classified so far

81.8%

Powered by data from:
OPEN REPAIR ALLIANCE

Impact on engagement:

The new design received mostly positive feedback from participants, and the additional complexity of asking different questions depending on the status of the device did not seem to cause too many issues. Despite our efforts to remove more low-quality data, we did still receive feedback that some of the source data was difficult to classify.

That said, the metrics suggest that our renewed focus on our core community seemed to work, with the average number of opinions submitted by logged in users more than doubling from 35 to 72, the highest to date. This was also helped by additional outreach activities, such as running an online social event for the community, in which we worked on BattCat together. The average number of opinions submitted per anonymous user session also increased slightly, from 19 to 20.

Average number of submissions per participant

The average number of submissions per participant increased overall for each task

Furthermore, the bounce rate and % exit rate continued to fall, outperforming the average rates for our main website. From this we can cautiously infer that very few users left the BattCat page without interacting with it and that only a small proportion left the site through this page.

	Average opinions per logged in user	Average opinions per anonymous user session	Bounce Rate	% Exit
PrintCat	48	5	5.56%	8.74%
TabiCat	40	19	2.00%	5.89%
BattCat	72	20	0.00%	2.24%

Conclusion & Learnings

User experience (UX) design is notoriously difficult. But while this exercise has reinforced that reputation for us, we have learned a lot through this process of iterating similar designs over multiple microtasks.

By making improvements to the design and flow of each microtask, we were able to increase engagement rates for both anonymous and logged-in users overall. The number of opinions submitted per user generally increased from task to task and the rate at which users left the page without interacting with it decreased.

Here are our key takeaways:

Accessibility first

Our early microtasks made total sense to us and to many of our most engaged community members. However, they were much harder to understand for those less familiar with our work. With each microtask, we tried to take an additional step back to consider how accessible it was to someone who had never encountered repair or Restart before. This primarily meant adding additional explainers and guidance, visually clarifying the flow of each microtask, supporting additional languages and adjusting our copy and messaging to better consider differing levels of prior knowledge.

Of course, this also meant addressing technical challenges, such as streamlining the mobile experience and fixing bugs.

Encourage feedback

Allowing users to offer feedback was crucial. Our community forum and social media channels were useful spaces for talking to users who found it hard to engage with the microtasks and learn what wasn't working for them. See [the forum conversation about PrintCat](#) as an example of this. This allowed us to address common problems while designing the next microtask and adjust our messaging to help set realistic expectations.

More fundamentally, the feedback from citizen scientists who joined us was very valuable, and helped us understand we need to continue improving the quality of the data we collect.

Prioritisation matters

While some of the improvements we made benefited every user, many decisions we made prioritised a certain type of user or a certain way to engage with the microtask. We saw this with TabiCat, where our focus on anonymous users seems to neglect slightly the needs/motivations of our core community. Ultimately, it is important to set clear objectives and consider the opportunity cost or side effects of such decisions.